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RUSSIAN CYBERWARFARE AND THE NATIONAL CYBER SECURITY POLICY IN UKRAINE: HOW TO OPTIMIZE THE NATIONAL RESEARCH POLICY?

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The author would like to acknowledge the valuable contribution of the following scholars in this research: Ye. Laniuk, Fulbright Research Program, PhD in Politics, and M. Lopata, Kirkland Research Program, PhD in Politics.

Cyberwarfare becomes extremely significant in contemporary conflicts. It includes, in particular, the disruption of national communications systems, their infiltration with harmful ideas, stealing of classified information, hacker attacks at national electronic networks, manipulations with public opinion in social media etc. This new form of warfare may not be followed by conventional combat actions.

This new type of cyber hostile actions calls for a re-definition of the traditional concept of war. Russia is definitely one of the countries that most actively resort to this new form of warfare. A large scale intrusion into the Ukrainian information space during the annexation of the Crimea and the ongoing war in the Donbass region provide apt examples of contemporary cyberwarfare. Due to the novelty of this type of warfare the measures of national security policy, which counter it, are not well established and need permanent research exploration. Therefore, the elaboration of national security measures in order to resist Russian cyberwarfare (RCW) is an issue of both theoretical and actual political importance.

These issues have been examined in the following publications. National security policies in response to cyber warfare, including the Russian hybrid one, were analysed by J. Andress [1], R.A. Clark [2], A. Collins [3], K. Geers [4], J. Healey [6], R.K. Knake [2], M.C. Libicki [7], Ye. Mahda [8], B.M. Mazanec [9], T. Rid [10], S. Winterfeld [1], and by many other scholars. Despite all this broad bibliography, there has been still no authoritative and comprehensive research regarding a national cybersecurity policy analysis in Ukrainian in response to RCW. That is why Ukrainian authorities need at least complex and verified research policy in this case.

It is obvious that the national cybersecurity research policy in Ukraine needs to be explored and optimized in a new way according to the Western research paradigm. We suppose that it shall be grounded mostly on two basic premises:

1. *Collaboration with western democracies as a countermeasure* — Ukraine and the Western powers have to facilitate their cooperation in order to counter Russian cyber aggression. The benefit of mutual cooperation is due to the fact that the Western countries have the most advanced technical, research and institutional capabilities to react to Russian threat. Ukraine has limited capabilities to resist it on its own and so it has to take over an American experience as well. At the same time, the RCW against Ukraine is massive and unprecedented in the world's scale, due to the combination of geographical proximity, common cultural, historical, and linguistic legacy, and informational infrastructure. The case of Russian-Ukrainian cyberwarfare is valuable for the study by any foreign researchers and policymakers.

2. *Comparative threat and response analysis as a recognition and evaluation measure* — despite geopolitical, military, socio-economic, and other differences between the Western democracies and Ukraine, RCW against them has a number of important common features, including forcing of hate speech in social media, spreading of fake news, computer virus attacks etc. Only comparative analysis will allow identifying the most efficient components of national security strategy in response to these threats.

The next step should be the determination of the goal and objectives for national cybersecurity research policy which is both diverse and complex. We could, at least, define them in a very concise form: the research policy should discover how national security measures in Ukraine can be enhanced and improved on the basis of Western policies and how the case and field experience of Ukraine can be instructive to the Western cybersecurity policy and counter measures.

In order to achieve these goals, the following methodology can be and shall be applicable:

1. *Comparative empirical analysis of the NSP*, based on the Global CyberSecurityIndex(GCI) approach [5], which includes the study of the following parameters:

- *legal* (legal institutions and frameworks dealing with cybersecurity at local, national, and international levels);

- *technical* (technical institutions and frameworks dealing with cybersecurity);

- *organizational* (policy coordination institutions and strategies from cybersecurity development);

- *capacity building* (research and development, education and training programmes, certified professionals and public sector agencies fostering capacity buildings);

- *cooperation* (partnerships, cooperative frameworks and information sharing networks).

2. *Qualitative research methods*, including *interviews* (with legislators, policymakers, government officials, legal experts, civil activists, researchers, and the military); *case study*; *expert focus polls*.

This methodological framework shall include *analysis of academic publications* about contemporary cyberwarfare, of the RCW against the West and Ukraine, the analysis of national security policies in these counties based on the GSI approach, the conclusion about their common and distinctive features; as well as the *qualitative expert analysis* of the national security policies in the form interviews and focus polls with paramount Western and Ukrainian experts, summarization and interpretation of the expert survey.

Optimization of national cybersecurity research policy of Ukraine, including institutions, policies and legal norms, on the basis of Western experience, is only one step to provide the national security in Ukraine. The other and most important step is the implementation in the actual national cybersecurity policy best practices described and prescribed by such research policy which is the natural obligation of Ukrainian policymakers. There is no doubt that both successful research and reasonable implementation of cybersecurity policy will Ukraine much more safe and protected nation.

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ЩОДО НОРМАТИВНОГО ЗМІСТУ ІМУНІТЕТУ ЗАХИСНИКА В КРИМІНАЛЬНОМУ ПРОЦЕСІ УКРАЇНИ

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Досліджуючи питання іmunітету захисника у кримінальному важливим є відокремлення переліку осіб, що визначені законодавцем у ч. 2 ст. 65 КПК та не можуть бути допитані у якості свідків. Так, у п. 1 зазначеної процесуальної норми вказується, що не може бути допитаний як свідок захисник ... про обставини, які стали йому відомі у зв'язку з виконанням функцій представника чи захисника. У свою чергу в п. 2 ч. 2 ст. 65 КПК, як ми вже зазначали, закріплене положення відповідно до якого не може бути допитаний як свідок адвокат - про відомості, які становлять адвокатську таємницю. Враховуючи положення ст. 131-2 Конституції та ст. 45 КПК виключно адвокат здійснює захист від кримінального обвинувачення, а отже як п. 1 так й п. 2 ч. 2 ст. 65 КПК стосуються одного й того ж учасника кримінального провадження – адвоката.

Аналіз змісту вказаних пунктів закону дозволяє дійти висновку, що обставини про які не можна допитувати адвоката є більшими за обсяг адвокатської таємниці. Так, адвокатська таємниця є інформацією, якою наділено обмежено коло осіб та яка стосується виключно клієнта та його інтересів. При цьому обставини, які можуть стати відомими адвокату під час реалізації ним правосуб'єктності захисника в окремому кримінальному провадженні можуть й не стосуватись адвокатської таємниці. Так, відповідно до ч. 2 ст. 22 ЗУ «Про адвокатуру та адвокатську діяльність», адвокатом під час реалізації функції захисту у кримінальному провадженні, окрім